

The Characterization of the Praxis of Interdisciplinary Research: The Energy for Sustainability Initiative case study

Danyela Samaniego Rascon ^{a,b*}, António G. Martins^b

^a *University of Coimbra, Institute for Interdisciplinary Research, Energy for Sustainability Initiative, Casa Costa Alemão- Pólo II, Rua Dom Francisco de Lemos, 3030-789, Coimbra, Portugal. danyela.rascon@uc.pt**

^b *University of Coimbra, INESC Coimbra, DEEC, Pólo II, R. Silvio Lima, 3030-290 Coimbra, Portugal.*

Purpose – This paper aims to provide information about Interdisciplinary Research related to the constitution of teams, funding search, barriers, and how these issues influence their research activities) through the characterization of the actual stage in terms of the effective involvement in IDR practice in the process in which a team science achieves solutions for energy and sustainability matters.

Design/methodology/approach – The paper presents an exploratory study using a qualitative approach, including interviews with researchers leading projects and knowledge management experts, besides, as an inquiry and workshop about “The praxis of interdisciplinary research in the context of the EfS Initiative: a first approach” were carried out within the research network.

Findings – The results showed that IDR practice has a high impact on researchers' professional paths. The primary motivation among researchers in conducting IDR is the search for solutions to real-world problems that affect social/economic development. Among the identified factors representing a difficulty for practicing IDR inside teams, were: team engagement, research priorities, communication and background–language differences, reconciling different disciplinary norms and practices (background-culture), and identification of partners for collaborations.

Practical implications – The paper includes implications for developing a Knowledge Management strategy to increase the efficiency of the collaborative process intrinsic to IDR science team initiatives focused on sustainable development goals.

Originality/value – This paper fulfills an identified need to study how IDR teams-science initiative achieves solutions for energy and sustainability matters.

Article Type: A case study

Keywords: Interdisciplinary Research; Sustainable Development; Energy; Sustainability; Collaborative Network; Research Network; Science of team science; Team management; Knowledge Management; Qualitative approach

Introduction

Society faces challenges that go beyond mono-disciplinary boundaries, many of them perceived as real-world problems. In order to solve these societal-pressing problems, most of them represented in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, knowledge, and understanding from different disciplines become essential. The Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by the United Nations Member States, comprises 17 Sustainable Development Goals and 169 targets in related thematic issues including water, energy, climate, oceans, urbanization, transport, science, and technology. In this context, Interdisciplinary scientific research (IDR) is viewed as a highly valued tool that unifies different fronts on science aiming to produce new knowledge through research collaborations across different research fields (Carr et al., 2018; Wagner et al., 2011).

Knowledge Management, Science of Team Science and Interdisciplinary Research

Knowledge is vital for creating value (Wehn and Montalvo, 2016). Exchanges of knowledge between disciplines have always been part of scientific life but, in the last quarter of the 20th century, interdisciplinarity developed in many areas of science and became a science policy priority despite strong structural obstacles. Nowadays, IDR and education are a major trend in universities and research funding agencies, at (sub) national and international levels (Wernli and Darbellay, 2016). Interdisciplinary teams, networks and initiatives have been created by different higher education institutions (HEI) as a strategy for the achievement of the SDG's agenda since teams, where the participants share and create knowledge, are known forms of strategic knowledge management (KM) and purposeful forum for IDR and cross-sectoral engagement (Watkins et al., 2018). Team Science is increasingly important due to researchers from different disciplines combining specialized expertise, theoretical approaches, and research methods across disciplinary boundaries in order to create knowledge that can be applied to solving complex problems (Börner et al., 2010; DeHart, 2017). In other words, knowledge networking helps to fill gaps across disciplinary boundaries, as well as, support researchers in their way of identifying suitable solutions for complex problems of common interests, regardless of time and space restrictions (Barão et al., 2017; Park and Gabbard, 2017). Besides, team science initiatives are designed to promote this collaborative (often cross-disciplinary) approaches (Stokols et al., 2008). The area of research focused on the processes by which scientific teams organize, communicate, and conduct research is called Science of team science (SciTS). It includes strategies that aim to understand and embed the collaborative processes and outcomes of team-based research (Falk et al., 2010; Little et al., 2017; Yu et al., 2018). While SciTS focuses on how teams connect and collaborate to achieve scientific breakthroughs (Börner et al., 2010), KM endorses and focuses on the process of creating, storing, integrating, sharing, applying, and leveraging knowledge (Becerra and Sabherwal, 2010; Wu et al., 2019)

Cross-disciplinary teams, whether utilizing approaches that are multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, or transdisciplinary are expected to achieve their objectives (Börner et al., 2010) and the capacity of team science to achieve those objectives relies on its performance which will define its effectiveness (National Research Council, 2015). According to the National Research Council (2015), large groups of scientists participating in IDR whose members developed a shared understanding of the research goals seems to be more likely in being successful in synthesizing their perceptions to achieve those goals.

Moreover, the integration of teams with science production purposes is not limited to the

cross-disciplinary constitution of the team. It means that the team members come from different disciplines, but also, institutions and nationalities which may face challenges within research procedures (Yu et al., 2018). To become effectively experienced and skilled in fields other than their own, teams should focus on understanding the connections between different knowledge communities (Lotrecchiano and Mirsa, 2018). The inefficiency of a network relies on a restricted understanding of how to conceptualize, develop and follow through on its strategic intentions of it (Creech and Willard, 2001). For knowledge networking to succeed, knowledge contribution needs to be initially perceived and longitudinally regarded as a worthwhile effort. For this reason, it is necessary to find out the key extrinsic motivations for knowledge sharing inside the network. It is also important to develop a shared understanding among all members, to contribute to strengthening knowledge management (Creech and Willard, 2001; National Research Council, 2015).

While interdisciplinarity has achieved a status of recognition, it has not reached its full potential due to the persistence of significant obstacles at many levels of the creation, sharing, and application of knowledge. For instance, researchers are not as motivated to share their data in the public domain as they are motivated in seeking open data. As the practice of IDR results from the collaboration of scholars from different disciplines, the management of collaborative research projects has become an important challenge requiring (new forms of) knowledge, methods, and skills (Becerra and Sabherwal, 2010; Park and Gabbard, 2017; Wernli and Darbellay, 2016).

Perhaps, the challenge is lowering those barriers to make IDR a real force in universities while continuing to build on the strength of the disciplines. According to Cummings et al. (2018), addressing the SDGs-identified challenges will require global efforts and advances in the field of Knowledge because its perception within the SDGs has not yet received the required attention.

According to Torabi and El-Den, 2017, the added value due to knowledge management depends on increasing individual, team, and organizational efficiency through the implementation of knowledge management concepts. To embed organizational effectiveness, knowledge management should play a key role in the creation, sharing, dissemination, and retention of knowledge. Technically, enhancing the effectiveness of IDR Team Science and Knowledge Management optimization within knowledge communities, networks, and Initiatives will contribute to the process of pursuing to meet the goals of the 2030 Agenda.

Methodology for identification of KM solutions

Orenga and Chalmeta (2019) provide a methodology integrated by phases that can be broken into activities and tasks. The methodology helps to collect, generate, manage and apply the knowledge generated inside and externally to the organization. The first step is to identify the needs and scope followed by planning, analysis, design, development, implementation, and control. Due to the diversity of goals, some authors (Stokols et al., 2008; 2010; Wooten et al., 2014) point out that team science initiatives require multiple quantitative and qualitative methods to measure their processes and outcomes. The authors suggest to include surveys and interviews of team members; behavioral observations of meetings and collaborative discussions; analyses of scientific productivity, such as impact based on content analyses and bibliometric assessments of initiative-based publications; focus-group meetings among scientists, trainees, and staff members participating in an initiative; online diary logs of cross-disciplinary encounters; social-network analyses of collaborative exchanges; peer reviews by

external referees and independent evaluations of progress reports and collaborative publications.

Due to the fact that team science initiatives differ in size, goals, duration, organizational structure, and cross-disciplinary scope (Stokols et al., 2008), they will ultimately have different needs in the process of KM adoption where the methodology used will eventually require some variations in order to fulfill those needs. According to Armaghan and Renaud (2017), the first stage of changing management through KM adoption is the diagnosis stage where the current status of an organization is identified. Burnette et al. (2013) call this first stage as “setting the scene” which is classified as a preliminary phase in the path of KM Strategy Development. Hence a phase of diagnosis for a case study will be discussed in the following sections. The current status towards the characterization of IDR practice will be analyzed. Through this analysis, it can be conceived how researcher conduct IDR, integrate IDR teams, secure financial support, and perceive the barriers to IDR practice. In other terms, how researchers create, capture, share and apply Knowledge in a particular IDR network of experts. The diagnosis phase will provide relevant information that could contribute to the identification of areas with opportunity for improvement. Eventually, the identified areas in the present study could empower the development of KM strategy in order to increase the efficiency of the collaborative process intrinsic to IDR science team initiatives focused on sustainable development goals.

Characterization of the Praxis of Interdisciplinary Research | Case Study

Section 2 presents the characterization of the IDR practice within a knowledge network and team science initiative taking the Energy for Sustainability (Efs) Initiative of the University of Coimbra, in Portugal, as a case study. The Efs Initiative brings together professors and researchers with a variety of backgrounds from more than a dozen of R&D Units. The members joining the Initiative have quite an experience in teaching and research in diverse scientific areas that converge in energy and sustainable development. This Network aims to transfer knowledge to society keeping a close connection to companies and other organizations. Besides, it manages advanced training activities, at the masters and doctoral levels. The activities are very much of an interdisciplinary nature. The Efs is structured in five committees in its organizational structure and more than one hundred researchers in its network.

The process of characterization of the praxis of IDR in the Efs Initiative was designed in several phases. In the first phase, Efs Initiative members with experience in leading research projects were interviewed. In the second phase, an online inquiry was launched inside the network. This was followed by a workshop about “the praxis of interdisciplinary research in the context of the Efs Initiative: a first approach” where the results of the inquiry were announced to the network in order to try to obtain some feedback from the Efs members. Finally, Experts in Knowledge Management were interviewed and gave their opinion on the topic.

Efs Project Leaders Interviews

In a phase of pre-diagnosis, project leaders in Interdisciplinary Research (IDR) within different Research Units under the Efs were interviewed. The interview series aimed to perceive how project leaders conduct IDR. In other words, how they integrate IDR teams,

look for financial support, perceive IDR barriers and virtues, and how these issues influence their research activities. The structured interviews and formulated questions for the interviewees were inspired by the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) report¹. The researchers that participated in the interview series (seven were men and two were women) had more than six years of experience in leading projects, some of them even more than ten. The audio-recorder interviews involved associated, full and auxiliary Professors from the fields of Law, Economy, Environmental Sciences, and Engineering (Civil, Chemical, Electrical, Mechanical, and Robotic).

The results showed that IDR practice and its impact on researchers' professional lives was classified as a very important matter. In terms of IDR involvement, approximately one-third of the researchers with more than 10 years of experience classified their work as totally IDR; while more than half of them classified it between 75% and 50 % IDR. In general, the practice of IDR within the research units was considered active.

Besides, “searching for the solution to real-world problems that affect social/economic development” is the main motivation among researchers in conducting IDR. It was followed by “curiosity-driven research” and “collaborations with academic and non-academic institutions”. Even though, the “access to private or public funding” was not neglected.

Research networks, researcher recruitment, and research collaborations (academic and non-academic partners) were identified as the approaches used to grow, support, and embed IDR. Moreover, project leaders considered that the EfS Initiative supports the IDR practice by influencing and/or creating a cultural ambient towards IDR inside its network.

So, what is the impact that the practice of IDR has on career progression, IDR teams and collaborations, funding, and research outcomes? From the researchers' perspective, IDR provides researchers with more learning opportunities through interaction with experts of different disciplines. Therefore, IDR is expected to generate societal impact and open new research fields. Even though the researchers (67%) agreed that IDR often provides better job opportunities in research, 56% of the interviewed researchers were concerned over the career progression of IDR teams' members.

In terms of collaborations, IDR, more likely, involves non-academic partners. Even though, it is less difficult for researchers to find partners within disciplinary approaches. Besides, researchers consider that IDR represents a challenge in working with collaborators.

Despite the fact that IDR practice does not essentially require co-location (researchers being physically present at one location) or relocation of researchers (researchers' displacement), communication among researchers was considered more difficult in IDR teams (represented by 56% of the answers).

Even though the interviewed researchers believe that IDR is often considered riskier than disciplinary approaches by funders due to some difficulties in producing strong research proposals, researchers disagree with the fact of IDR is often considered with lower quality. Based on the answers, it is not clear enough if IDR is considered to be undervalued by research evaluators or if the reviewer's perspective plays a role in IDR being less likely to be funded than monodisciplinary approaches. On the other hand, opinions are even on the existence of a lack of research funding in general (or difficulties in obtaining funding in

¹ produced by the United Kingdom Technopolis Group -<http://www.technopolis-group.com/>

general).

In terms of research outcomes, researchers agreed with IDR outcomes being more likely to be published in journals with broader audiences and having the potential of becoming highly cited. About 56% of the EfS members who lead projects consider IDR outcomes are more likely to meet R&D Units priorities besides IDR doesn't necessarily require more time to produce research outcomes. Also, researchers believe that IDR is less likely to be published in top-tier mono-disciplinary journals, due to peers in researchers' core disciplines often considering IDR less rigorous. In addition, finding appropriate reviewers was considered a challenge for the experienced researchers.

In resume, the concerns and/or areas of improvement opportunity within IDR practice identified by project leaders were career progression, communication among researchers in IDR teams, finding partners within IDR approaches, collaborations among partners in IDR practice, difficulties in obtaining funding, production of strong research proposals, and Finding appropriate reviewers.

Fig. 1 represents diagrammatically a tentative synthesis of the ideas of the interviewed project leaders on the possible paths toward IDR knowledge integration. The depicted nodes can assume different natures, such as activities, outcomes, phases, or even initial steps of a path toward the bottom line node, which is the integration of knowledge. The existence of a cultural influence within the community is both the result of praxis and a favorable context to IDR, which is likely to evolve per se to the definition of IDR streams or lines of research since mutual knowledge on competencies and fields of work among researchers ease up the way to the identification of potential cross-cutting views on how to transform reality. In this framework, curiosity-driven research projects may lead to more easily identifying and grasping funding opportunities for launching important funded projects, as well as funding opportunities can also trigger the identification of projects that the installed IDR culture enables. Either way, collaborative teams are to be set up, involving academia or industry, both benefiting from networks, formal or informal, and originating or reinforcing those networks. The starting node of a particular project/process is thus uncertain but it always lies on culture and leads to knowledge integration.

Fig. 1. Common components in IDR practice

In practice, there are difficulties to overcome. It seems the most important one is the fact that research leaders' time is scarce. Senior researchers are usually overloaded with

responsibilities and tasks, oftentimes not directly related to research, which is detrimental even to fundraising. Besides, researchers should not be supposed to fully master the art and science of writing successful funding applications, specific skills of third parties being usually very effective for the purpose. However, a second difficulty stands in the way, either structural or financial: the scarcity of available specialized staff. The existence of funded projects has the additional advantage of more easily attracting advanced students to research, through scholarships and grants.

Lack of time also influences the intensity of the efforts towards sharing experiences and knowledge on the skills, capacity, and fields of work among the Initiative members. Since IDR practice is a dynamic process, requiring constant refreshing, besides meetings, workshops, and conferences, some mechanisms to promote the integration of knowledge could eventually play an important role in improving collaborations, which requires time and the absence of rush for appropriate reflection to take place.

EfS Knowledge Network

An inquiry was launched inside the EfS Initiative, which had 131 researchers in its network at the time of the inquiry. The questions were inspired by the report of the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) produced by the United Kingdom Technopolis group (<http://www.technopolis-group.com/>). The inquiry did not include attention-check questions since the need to remove some replies from a data set may introduce a bias in the results of the data (McKibben and Silvia, 2016; Kung et al. 2018; Malone and Lusk, 2019).

The response rate was near 50% (65 researchers). 70% of the respondents are 41 to 60 years old. Also, 70% are men and 87% are Portuguese citizens. 73% are Professors, and 98% have a full-time position at the University. The dominant disciplinary background was Engineering and Technology with 67% of the cases. The other fields with a lower number of researchers were Economics, Natural Sciences, Management, Architecture, Psychology, Exact Sciences, Law, Public Policy Studies and Sociology.

Two-thirds of the respondents consider their research to be 50% or more IDR. Only in the case of Psychology, the average percentage of effort dedicated to IDR is low (9%), the remaining cases being always superior to 25%, although with an upper bound of 60%. A monotonous trend is identifiable in the time dedicated to IDR as a function of age: it goes from 42% to 26% in the age intervals from 31-40 to 60+ respectively, denoting a possible higher awareness of younger researchers of the need/advantages of IDR to deal with contemporary problems related to energy and sustainability. Curiously enough, given that the EfS Initiative is interdisciplinary in nature, 6% of the respondents consider not practicing IDR. This finding does not dismiss the fact that 100% of the respondents consider IDR as important or very important. It confirms the general understanding expressed by interviewed project leaders that multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and transdisciplinary perspectives are always needed, and mutual collaboration, networking, and resource and knowledge sharing are critical for success in all scientific and technical fields.

Since the EfS Initiative gathers together researchers from a number of R&D units, these are at the front line of the interface with researchers and provide them the specific environment that can be more or less stimulating of IDR, the EfS Initiative being a second-level framing environment for cross-cutting perspectives on scientific activity. The majority of the researchers (83%) believe that IDR practice is supported and often supported at a general level by their R&D units. Infrastructure and IDR cultural influence, followed by funding and management procedures and practices received approximately equivalent numbers of votes.

When the same questions were asked about the EfS Initiative, IDR Cultural influence received 43% of the votes while financial support in activities of dissemination and science communication and management procedures and practices were identified with similar relative importance, between 28% and 29%. There is a significant difference between the relative importance of the cultural influence exerted by the Initiative and the one exerted by R&D units, which means that researchers perceive a specific role played by the Initiative toward stimulating IDR.

The main concerns on factors that can negatively influence the decision to undertake IDR are lack of funding or difficulties in obtaining funding, as well as difficulties in finding collaborators or challenges in working with collaborators of different scientific backgrounds. These four factors were all considered very influential or influential by more than 70% of the respondents. There are some differences in perception though, depending on the age of researchers [Fig. 2]. Researchers between ages 30 and 40 are concerned about career progression, besides, working and finding collaborators and funding. Those researchers who are between 41 and 60 years old are concerned about publishing, collaborations, and funding. Almost 50% of the interviewed researchers who are in their 50s are worried about IDR practice not being a priority. Besides, researchers 60+ years of age give lower importance to the non-financial factors than their younger colleagues, which may stem from their higher experience in team leading and people management in general. On the other hand, financial issues are a general concern.

Fig. 2. Influential factors in considering undertaking IDR according to the age of the researcher

IDR was not always a focus of science funding. However, researchers have statistically even opinions on the probability of obtaining funding for IDR and for monodisciplinary research. Fig. 3 shows how opinions are divided on this topic.

Fig. 3. Funding: IDR vs disciplinary research

The details of the opinions which consider IDR to be not so well funded as monodisciplinary research show that the two main factors identified are monodisciplinary research being more likely to be funded because of the disciplinary focus of funding opportunities (64%) and, on the other hand, the usual monodisciplinary perspective of reviewers who appreciate funding applications (84%). There is also concern about the possibility of IDR being considered riskier (53%) and therefore less likely to receive funding.

94% of the researchers, members of the Initiative, develop IDR in teams (mostly in teams of 3-8 members). Science teams composed of people with diverse backgrounds may reveal several kinds of detrimental factors affecting the research process [Fig. 4]. The ones that had around 60% or more of the opinions were difficulties regarding team engagement (degree of investment of time and effort by team members), potentially disparate research priorities, background–language differences affecting communication, reconciling different disciplinary norms and practices among diverse background scientific culture standards. In spite of these difficulties, the majority (94%) of the respondents considered IDR provides more learning opportunities through interactions with experts of other disciplines. Additionally, 70% of the respondents showed a clear awareness of the need of a strong disciplinary training as an essential foundation of effective IDR. In view of these opinions, the framework provided by the EfS Initiative may be considered at least an adapted environment to IDR, irrespectively of which cause is and which effect is: the EfS framework influencing researchers’ mindset or especially aware group of researchers creating an IDR stimulating environment such as the EfS Initiative. This perspective is emphasized by some of the results obtained from a section of the inquiry dedicated to “barriers and virtues, as illustrated in Fig. 5. Although 81% of the respondents consider a challenge finding appropriate reviewers for IDR applications, also 81% consider IDR has the potential to have a (positive) societal impact and an impressive 97% consider IDR advantageous for opening new research fields.

Factors that represent a difficulty in practicing IDR inside multidisciplinary teams

Fig. 4. Difficulties in practicing IDR teams

IDR barriers and virtues: Research outcomes

Fig. 5. IDR barriers and virtues: Research outcomes

Two complementary noteworthy aspects of IDR difficulties and virtues are 50% of the respondents consider that IDR is more likely to involve non-academic partners than monodisciplinary research, although 59% also claim that it is more difficult to identify partners for IDR practice.

Amidst the comments conveyed with the inquiry, one can easily find convergent opinions on the virtues of IDR: The main advantage of widening expertise knowledge while doing

integrated efforts, researching complex technical solutions or systems that highly depend on human use or interaction, is related to the opportunity to discuss interdisciplinary problems with researchers with different backgrounds and perspectives of the problems to be solved.

If this kind of interactions where the knowledge is shared or transferred became frequent at some point, the now continuous interactions could transform into a research network that not only could open up new research perspectives and research lines but also could improve the outcome through the integration of knowledge from experts with different backgrounds. This, from the perspective of the researchers, could improve the quality of the research outcomes compared to the sum of the outcomes from different disciplines working separately.

Workshop on IDR practice

A workshop about “The praxis of interdisciplinary research in the context of the EfS Initiative: a first approach” was carried out within the EfS community with the objective of revealing and discussing the results of the survey and interviews. Besides, the discussion is meant to answer some questions about the true meaning behind each statistical evidence of the results, the actual role of the EfS Initiative in IDR, and the barriers to IDR practice.

The workshop was an opportunity to face to face exchange of opinions on the role played by the EfS Initiative on the researchers’ activity and on the difficulties and possible paths ahead. The testimonies and opinions were far more abundant than it fits into the length of the present paper, which led to choosing those which correspond either to emphasize or confirm some of the conclusions from the previous phases or to new perspectives on opportunities to be explored.

General considerations about IDR in the context of the Initiative revealed two different perspectives: on one hand, the Initiative was considered an effective platform for stimulating IDR among the participant researchers but, on the other hand, some argued there are some personal attributes, such as vocation or interest, which are necessary to create receptivity in researchers to commit to IDR. There was consensus on the perception of a contemporary trend to favor IDR practice, which leads researchers to look for different competencies to carry out collaborations that can provide mutual benefit. This is in contrast with the absence of formal mechanisms to foster interdisciplinary collaboration, both at large and inside the Initiative itself. In order to identify possible mechanisms and best practices which can help to increase IDR practice within the network, researchers believe that it would be necessary to evaluate the mechanisms used up to now, identify their odds to try to improve them, along with search for additional paths. Some proposals were briefly made, such as a repository of information about members of the Initiative (that could help the integration and dissemination of information related to the competencies of the knowledge network), technological mechanisms for promoting the crossing of areas (promote collaborations) and an internal database on research outcomes. One particular remark was made acknowledging the apparent effectiveness of the prevailing IDR culture within the Initiative to stress that it should not be taken for granted in the absence of formal mechanisms.

One particular difficulty associated with IDR was identified as the undervaluation, by evaluators, of interdisciplinary project applications for funding, which follows short the usual practice of funding agencies of opening calls focused on rigid discipline boundaries. There are some signs of a possible change of this habit, particularly in the case of the Portuguese science funding agency, since in the most recent process of performance assessment of

research units there was the possibility of R&D units assuming an interdisciplinary label.

Researchers keen on IDR also have the responsibility of helping younger generations to acknowledge the importance of IDR, either by their direct contact with students or by influencing institutional decisions and strategies towards creating opportunities to cross knowledge domain boundaries at an earlier stage of the graduation process, leading to a new generation of researchers with an interdisciplinary vision and an established IDR culture.

Interview with experts

Two interviews were conducted with experts in Knowledge Management with different profiles, in order to get insights on further aspects that should be taken into consideration in a case study such as the present one.

The first one, a member of a research group working with Information Technologies (IT) for knowledge management, a Professor and coordinator of a postgraduate program, considers that KM is a wide topic where different disciplinary areas could be involved. The members of the academic body of this research group come from different technological areas. Besides, they receive students with different academic backgrounds in a postgraduate program. This Professor highlighted the importance of a strong monodisciplinary base to ensure competencies in interdisciplinary research. In reference to the present study, this expert expressed the opinion that the nature of a project that links knowledge networks, interdisciplinary research, and knowledge management, ends up being also an interdisciplinary project, meaning that while the topic is being researched it will also put IDR into practice.

The second interviewee is a Professor at the Faculty of Psychology, an expert in KM consulting. She considered that the present study complies with the standard practice of using both quantitative data, gathered through questionnaires, and qualitative data collected through interviews and a workshop that corresponds to a focus group discussion. Document analysis can provide additional insights into the organization, such as activity reports. The fact that the Initiative is not a formal organizational structure of the university, is not obliged to mandatory regular reporting, should not be a reason to overlook this potential source of information. Also, according to this expert's opinion, two important pillars should be considered in KM: organizational culture and leadership.

In the case of organizational culture, formal structured approaches usually lead to obtaining a sufficiently accurate image from a KM perspective. However, informal approaches are very valuable as a complementary tool: contact with researchers in an informal context, outside meetings, and focus group sessions, most of the time in a social life context. In fact, organizations tend to have two dimensions, one formal and one informal, and it is relevant to try to gain access to both. From a KM perspective, it is important to find out what is the nature of the knowledge people decide to share when they formally meet or work together and what knowledge people share in an informal situation.

The leadership pillar has also to be assessed in order to define the type of existing leadership. In theory, one can say that there are three sorts of leadership - virtuous leadership, toxic leadership, and leadership of empowerment (that empowers team members to be actors in the projects and in whatever needs to be done). KM is not compatible with self-centered and autocratic leadership. Therefore, analyzing the profile of leadership in the EfS network can bring important elements to perceive how it influences the course of actions.

Obtaining the opinions of the interviewed experts was in itself a step of the adopted methodology for the present study. These opinions have two important aspects. The first is a confirmation of the adequacy of the chosen path so far. The second is a set of directions for future work which the authors intend to follow, some of them actually being on their way at the time of writing.

Conclusion

Society faces challenges, most of them represented in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (adopted by the United Nations Member States) that comprises 17 Sustainable Development Goals and 169 targets in related thematic issues including water, energy, climate, oceans, urbanization, transport, science, and technology. In this context, knowledge and understanding from different disciplines become essential. Interdisciplinary research brings different backgrounds together to share and create knowledge around an issue of common interest where collaborations and research networks are vital bridges in the search for solutions to those problems that negatively impact the prosperity of human societies.

Due to the complexity of the issues at stake, cross-disciplinary teams and knowledge networks are becoming a starting point in solving a variety of issues. Team science initiatives are designed to promote cross-disciplinary collaborations in order to provide answers to research questions of complex problems. Therefore, understanding the connections between different knowledge communities could bring success in fulfilling shared interests and achieving common goals.

The present research aims to contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the area of team science effectiveness, in its first approach of characterization of the praxis of Interdisciplinary Research represented by a case study. The diagnosis stage aimed to obtain the clearest possible picture of several aspects of the Initiative: how IDR science teams are being integrated, the search for financial support, how EfS members perceive IDR barriers, and how these issues influence their research activities. It is expected that the outcome allows visualizing the actual stage of a knowledge network in terms of the effective involvement in IDR practice in the process in which a team science initiative achieves solutions for energy and sustainability matters.

In the first phase of the characterization stage assessment, EfS Initiative members with experience in leading research projects were interviewed. In the second phase, an inquiry was launched inside the research network. This was followed by a Workshop about “the praxis of interdisciplinary research in the context of the EfS Initiative: a first approach” where the results of the inquiry and interviews were announced to the network and members of the Initiative gave their feedback. Finally, experts in Knowledge Management were asked to give their opinion on the matter.

The main researchers’ motivation in conducting IDR was searching for the solution to real-world problems that affect social/economic development. Research Networks and researcher recruitment were identified as the approaches used to grow, support and embed IDR. Two-thirds of the respondents consider their research to be 50% or more IDR. The involvement in IDR practice, compared to those researchers who are in their 30’s, tends to decrease by 16% in those researchers more than 60 years old. Above 70% of the researchers believe that difficulties in obtaining funding, the challenges of working with collaborators with different backgrounds, and difficulties in finding collaborators are factors that influence their decision

on conducting IDR.

94% of the researchers, and members of the Initiative, develop IDR in teams. Among the identified factors representing a difficulty for practicing IDR inside teams, were: team engagement (degree of investment of time and effort), research priorities, communication and background–language differences, reconciling different disciplinary norms and practices (background culture), and identification of partners for collaborations.

In order to increase the efficiency of the collaborative process intrinsic to IDR science team initiatives focused on sustainable development goals, this paper aims to contribute information that could help the development or improvement of a KM strategy. Through a diagnosis, this investigation targets the identification of the areas of improvement opportunity for the future definition and identification of KM solutions applicable in the Initiative defined previously as a case study. Following the quantitative and qualitative analysis and as a complementary analysis to the exploratory phase/diagnosis, an analysis of documents/reports, interviews with the members of the core management structure of the Initiative, and an analysis of social network nodes will be carried out, in agreement with the opinions of the experts who were consulted.

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